

EFFECT OF AFOBAZOLE ON REPRODUCTIVE TOXICITY OF TOBACCO SMOKE IN RATS

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Materials and research methods: To study the effects of tobacco smoke on DNA damage in placental and embryonic tissues, antenatal and postnatal development of rats exposed to tobacco smoke

2) To evaluate the effect of afobazole on tobacco DNA damage in placenta and embryos using the DNA comet method at doses of 1 and 10 mg / kg daily until days 1-13 of pregnancy. rats.

3) To study the effect of afobazole orally at doses of 1 and 10 mg / kg per day throughout pregnancy on the manifestation of reproductive toxicity in rats exposed to tobacco smoke.

4) Using a T-maze behavioral test, evaluate the effect of afobazole on the formation of conditioned reflexes in rats exposed to tobacco smoke during pregnancy.

5) To compare the data obtained in the study of the effects of afobazole on the offspring of “smoking” rats with oral prenatal, postpartum, and prenatal and postpartum combination drug treatment regimens.

Scientific novelty. An experimental model of “passive smoking” has been proposed and described, which reveals the negative effects of tobacco smoke on antenatal and postnatal development in rat puppies. For the first time, the genotoxic effects of tobacco smoke on embryonic tissues and the placenta were described by the DNA comet method, and increased DNA damage in the placenta and embryonic cells was shown. For the first time, fundamental possibilities of reducing the genotoxic and reprotoxic effects of tobacco smoke on embryonic cells and placenta by using afobazole at doses of 1 and 10 mg / kg in prenatal, postpartum, and postpartum animals were identified.

Results and its discussion: There are more than 1.1 billion smokers worldwide, with the proportion of male and female smokers being about 60% and 20% in the Russian Federation, 30% and 28% in the UK, and 28% and 24% in the United States.]. In other words, at least a quarter of the

population in developed countries is a smoker. Russia is the world leader in the number of smokers. In 2009, there were 44 million tobacco users in the country, accounting for about 40 percent of the population.

However, the most toxic “second-hand” smoke from the burning end of a cigarette, along with the tobacco smoke usually emitted by a smoker, affects a third of 14 adults and about 40 percent of children on a regular basis. in the world [192]. Despite convincing evidence of the dangers of smoking, relatively few tobacco users around the world are fully aware of the health risks of smoking for themselves and others [109]. According to the World Health Organization's Global Tobacco Epidemic Report (2009), tobacco use is one of the leading causes of preventable death, affecting more than 5 million people worldwide each year. continues to kill, and this places an (direct) economic burden on people and countries. costs include health care, indirect costs are associated with declining labor productivity) [56].

There is more than 50 years of reliable scientific evidence on the health risks of smoking, in particular the risk of developing lung cancer and other malignant tumors, cardiovascular pathology, chronic respiratory diseases and other adverse effects. The program was obtained long ago [198]. However, in addition to smokers, non-smokers who breathe air containing “second-hand” tobacco smoke also increase the risk of illness and death, as confirmed by many studies [224]. Exposure to tobacco smoke accounts for about 1% of the total disease burden in the world and about 10-15% of the disease burden resulting from active smoking. However, in non-smokers exposed to passive smoking, the risk of lung cancer is increased by 34% and cardiovascular disease by 54% [41, 114].

Conclusions: The negative impact of environmental genotoxicants on human health, in particular on the developing organism in the uterus, and the formation of congenital pathologies under their influence stimulates the solution of problems of practical importance - pharmacological research, development, research and introduction. substances with antimutagenic properties as correctors of reprotoxic effects.

One of the most common geno- and reprotoxic factors is smoking. Actively promoting the risk of smoking does not lead to the expected result, the share of smokers almost does not decrease, and even increases among women of childbearing age [14, 15]. In addition, 11% to 36% of women do not give up drugs during pregnancy [71].

This study was conducted using the experimental model of “passive smoking” and was devoted to a comprehensive study of the genotoxic and

reprotoxic effects of tobacco smoke on offspring during antenatal and postnatal development and the effects of anxiolytic afobazole on this effect. has antioxidant and antimutagenic properties.

Conclusion:

1. Necessary and sufficient conditions for keeping animals in the atmosphere of tobacco smoke have been identified to solve the problem of modeling the genotoxic and reprotoxic effects of “passive smoking” without increasing the mortality of pregnant rats.

2. From the 1st to the 13th day of pregnancy, the effects of tobacco smoke significantly, 4 to 10 times, increase DNA damage in placental cells, the head and body of rat embryos.

3. Exposure to tobacco smoke during pregnancy reduces the weight gain of pregnant rats, has a pronounced embryotoxic effect, inhibits the formation of sensory-motor reflexes in offspring and conditioned reflex activity.

4. Afobazole is administered orally at a dose of 1 or 10 mg / kg daily until days 1-13 of pregnancy, significantly reducing or eliminating DNA damage caused by tobacco smoke in satellite cells and embryos of rats.

5. Afobazole (1 and 10 mg / kg) in combined prenatal, postnatal, and prenatal and postpartum use reduces reproductive toxicity and the inhibitory effect of tobacco smoke on the development of conditioned reflexes.

6. In all variants of experiments, the protective effect observed when using afobazole at a dose of 1 mg / kg is more quantitative, which is equal to the maximum daily dose of the drug recommended (30-60 mg) based on clinical indications. is coming. learn

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